

Effect of Nanoclay on the Mechanical Properties and Shrinkage Control of Low Profile Unsaturated Polyester Resins Cured at Low Temperatures

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ABSTRACT

Unsaturated polyester (UP) nanocomposites were prepared by dispersing organically modified montmorillonite in the polyester resin, followed by redox polymerization. Density measurements showed that a small amount of nanoclay (1-3 wt%) can improve the shrinkage control of the UP/styrene (St)/polyvinyl acetate (PVAc) system cured at room temperature. PVAc serves as the low profile additive (LPA). Both temperature-induced phase separation and TEM observation of the cured sample showed that almost all of the nanoclay resided in the LPA-rich phase or at the interface, which led to a higher reaction rate in the LPA-rich phase and earlier onset of micro-cracking in the LPA-rich phase or at the interface. Consequently, an earlier volume expansion during curing was observed in the reactive dilatometry experiment, leading to better shrinkage control.

X-ray diffraction showed a weak and broad peak with the clay d-spacing increased from 2.4 to 3.5 nm. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) showed that the morphology of the UP nanocomposite is a mix of intercalated and exfoliated clay sheets. The presence of clay particles enhanced the tensile modulus, but reduced the tensile strength of the UP nanocomposites. The fracture toughness parameter K_{IC} was improved 30% with the addition of 5 wt% nanoclay. The system with mixed nanoclay and calcium carbonate was found to possess the highest K_{IC} without sacrificing the tensile strength.

Key Words: Nanoclay, unsaturated polyester resin, low temperature cure, nanocomposite, low profile additive, shrinkage control.

INTRODUCTION

Unsaturated polyester resins are one of the mostly used materials in fabricated composites, which represent approximately $\frac{3}{4}$ of the total thermoset composites market by tonnage [Mark, et al., 1988]. However, UP composites have relatively poor thermal stability, toughness, flammability, and barrier properties. A new approach to improve these properties is to incorporate layered silicate into the polymer matrix, which is known as polymer-layered silicates (PLS) nanocomposites [Alexandre, 2000]. Another research impetus is the potential to achieve better volume shrinkage control of unsaturated polyester/styrene/low profile additive (UP/St/LPA) system cured at low temperature by employing a small amount of PLS into the system. Low profile additives (LPAs) have been found to be very effective in volume shrinkage control of UP resins cured in high-temperature processes, such as compression molding of sheet molding compounds (SMCs) and injection molding of bulk molding compounds (BMCs). However, the LPA effect in low-temperature processes such as resin transfer molding (RTM), Seemann

composites resin infusion molding process (SCRIMP) and hand lay-up/spray-up is still very limited and relies much on the resin structure [Li, et al., 1998].

In this work, we investigate the structure and property relationship of layered silicate UP nanocomposites. The effect of nanoclay loading, particle size on tensile property, and fracture toughness of the resulting UP nanocomposites is discussed. We found that shrinkage control of a UP/St/LPA system cured at low temperature can be greatly improved by introducing a small amount of nanoclay into the resin system. A temperature-forced phase separation and transmission electron microscopy (TEM) was used to investigate the nanoclay partition in the LPA-rich and UP-rich phases in order to explore the shrinkage control mechanism.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

The UP resin used in this study was Q6585 from Ashland Chemical. Q6585 is a 1:1 maleic anhydride (MA) and propylene glycol (PG) mixture with an average of 10.13 vinylene groups per molecule and an average molecular weight of 1560 g mol^{-1} , and contains 35 wt% styrene. The crosslinking monomer used was styrene (St) from Aldrich (Milwaukee, WI). The LPA used in this study was Neulon-T plus, a modified poly(vinyl acetate) (PVAc) from Union Carbide (now Dow Chemical). The nanoclay, Cloisite[®] 20A (Southern Clay), is a natural montmorillonite modified with a quaternary ammonium chloride having two hydrogenated tallovs (~65% C_{18} ; ~30% C_{16} ; ~5% C_{14}). The calcium carbonate ($CaCO_3$) filler provide by Ashland Chemical has an average particle size of 4 μm . All the samples tested were formulated to provide an St C=C double bond to UP C=C double bond ratio of 2.0. The initiator used was methyl ethyl ketone peroxide (MEKP, Aldrich) and the promoter was cobalt octoate (Pfaltz & Bauer).

Casting

After the UP resin was mixed with styrene, BQ, promoter, and a certain amount of nanoclay Cloisite[®] 20A was added to the resin mixture. Mechanically stirred followed by sonication for 2 hrs, the mixture was cooled to room temperature and the initiator MEKP was added. Finally, the monomer mixture was spread as a thin panel by sandwiching it between two mold release agent-coated glass plates. The two glass plates were separated by an U-shaped rubber ring, held in place by clamps. The panel was cured at room temperature for 24 hours followed by post curing in an oven at 200°C. The panels were then cut into tensile and fracture specimens for testing.

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC 2920, TA Instruments) was used to measure the reaction exotherm. The sample was sealed in a volatile aluminum sample pan that can stand up to 2 atm internal pressure. Isothermal runs were followed by a scanning from room temperature to 250°C with a heating rate of 5°C/min to determine the residual heat. The total reaction exotherm was calculated from the area under the isothermal and scanning DSC curves. The exotherm data can be converted to reaction rate and conversion as a function of time by combining the total reaction exotherm.

Density measurement

Density measurement of the cured sample was employed in this study in order to calculate the volume shrinkage of the resin system. About five grams of a resin mixture were heat-sealed in a rectangular plastic pouch with a dimension of 70×60 mm. The sealed sample pouch was degassed under vacuum. After that, air bubbles inside the pouch were squeezed out through a small hole poked at the edge of the pouch. The pouch was heat sealed again and sandwiched between two aluminum plates. The sample was cured isothermally either in an oven or a water bath. The density of the cured samples was determined by weighing the samples in air and in water, respectively. The density of the cured sample (ρ_s) and the volume shrinkage can be calculated by using the following equations:

$$\rho_s = \rho_{H_2O} \times W_s / (W_s - W_w) \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Volume Shrinkage (\%)} = (1 - \rho_{s_0} / \rho_s) \times 100 \quad (2)$$

in which ρ_{s_0} is the density of the resin mixture before cure and ρ_{H_2O} is the density of water at 25°C. W_s and W_w are the sample weights when measured in air and in water, respectively.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

The fracture surface of the sample cured in the density measurement (without etching by any solvent) was gold-coated and observed by a Philip XL-30 scanning electron microscopy (SEM) with 10kV power. During observation, the magnification varied from 100X to 2,000X depending on the sample morphology.

X-ray diffraction (XRD)

The average clay dispersion was analyzed by an X-ray diffractometer (XRD), Scintag XDS-2000, which was equipped with an intrinsic germanium detector system using Cu K α radiation ($\lambda=1.5418\text{\AA}$).

Transmission electron microscopy (TEM)

Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) was also used to characterize the nanocomposites structure, especially to get visual information about the clay dispersion and location. The specimen was microtomed into ultrathin slices (<100nm) using an ultracryomicrotome equipped with a diamond knife. TEM observation was performed on a Phillip CM200 using an accelerating voltage of 200kV.

Tensile tests

Tensile tests were performed at a displacement rate of 5.08 mm/min on an Instron tensile tester equipped with an extensometer according to tensile standard ([ASTM D638](#)). Five specimens were tested for each sample.

Fracture toughness testing

Three-point bending specimens with [ASTM E399](#) dimensions ($W=1.0$ cm and $B=0.35$ cm) were cut from the nanocomposite panels using a diamond saw. The specimens were prenotched by a sharp circular diamond saw followed by inserting a fresh razor blade and tapping to initiate a natural crack. The total crack length a (crack prenotch plus razor notch) is equal to 0.35 cm. The specimens were then loaded into a three-point bending test fixture of a universal-testing machine

(MTS Instron 4204). The cross-head speed was kept at 0.038 mm/second and the maximum load to failure (P_c , KN) was recorded. Six to eight specimens were tested for each type of nanocomposite. The fracture toughness K_{IC} was calculated using the following formula:

$$K_{IC} = (P_c S / BW^{3/2}) \cdot f(a/W)$$

in which:

$$f(a/W) = \frac{3(a/W)^{1/2} [1.99 - (a/W)(1 - a/W)(2.15 - 3.93a/W + 2.7a^2/W^2)]}{2(1 + 2a/W)(1 - a/W)^{3/2}}$$

P_c (KN) is the maximum fracture load in a three-point bending test; S (cm) is the span between two support points; B (cm) is the specimen thickness in the crack plane, W (cm) is the specimen depth (width) in the crack propagation direction; a (cm) is the total crack length (crack prenotch plus razor notch).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Effect of nanoclay on reaction kinetics and volume shrinkage

In the reaction kinetic and shrinkage control study, all samples contained 3.5 wt% LPA. Benzoquinone (BQ) at 300 ppm as introduced to allow a longer induction time for sample preparation.

To investigate the effect of nanoclay on the reaction rate, the curing of the resin mixtures with different clay content was monitored by DSC at 35°C. Figures 1a and 1b show the reaction rate and conversion of the resin system with different clay content, respectively. With a higher clay content, the reaction rate increases and the induction time decreases; however, the final resin conversion is independent of the clay content. The clay may act as a co-promoter in the redox polymerization of the UP/St/LPA resin system. Another possibility is that the viscosity increases when nanoclay is introduced into the resin system.

Table 1 presents density and volume shrinkage of the samples cured at 26°C in a water bath. The final shrinkage of the cured sample is around 2.97% and -1.44% for the systems with 1.5 and 3 wt% clay. They are much lower than that of the system without nanoclay, 6.96% final shrinkage. The two samples with nanoclay were stark white (opaque) in appearance, while the one without nanoclay was translucent. The stark white appearance is an evidence of the microvoid formation in the sample, corresponding to good shrinkage control.

In order to study the influence of reaction rate on the final volume shrinkage of the UP resin system, we prepared a sample with a reduced amount of promoter/initiator, but with the same 3 wt% nanoclay. This sample has almost the same reaction rate profile as the pure resin with a higher promoter/initiator content (Figure 2). The appearance of this sample cured in a 26°C water bath was also stark white (opaque) and the final volume shrinkages was about 2.11%, while being much lower than that of the pure resin (6.96%) (Table 1). It is obvious that a higher reaction rate alone cannot improve the volume shrinkage control. A small amount of nanoclay does improve the volume shrinkage of the UP/St/LPA system cured at room temperature.

In order to study the effect of nanoclay on the shrinkage control of the UP/St/LPA system, the final morphology of the samples was observed under SEM. Figure 3 shows the fracture surface of the sample containing 3.5% LPA with different amounts of nanoclay, after curing in a 26°C water bath. Figure 3a shows the morphology of the sample without nanoclay, revealing a two-phase structure. The particulate region (LPA-rich) is small and forms the dispersed phase

with diameter less than 20 μm , in which spherical particles with diameters ranging from 1 to 5 μm are loosely packed. The flake-like region (UP-rich) forms the continuous phase. With 1.5% nanoclay, the LPA-rich phase (particulate) and the UP-rich phase (flake-like) become co-continuous, as shown in [Figure 3b](#). The particulate phase also consists of loosely packed spherical particles with diameters ranging from 1 to 5 μm . By further increasing the nanoclay content to 3%, the structure of the samples is similar to that with 1.5% nanoclay, except that the size of both the particulate region and the flake-like region becomes smaller, as shown in [Figure 3c](#). Under the same nanoclay and LPA loading, the reaction rate did not significantly change the sample morphology ([Figure 3d](#)). Different morphological structures resulting from different clay loading strongly affect the size of the LPA rich phase area, and thus the shrinkage control.

In the UP/St/LPA system, the polar thermoplastic PVAc (dipole moment of 1.6) tends to phase out during curing because the more polar, unreacted UP resin (dipole moment of 2.0-2.5) becomes less polar (dipole moment of less than 1.0) as reaction progresses. A reaction-induced phase separation results in a UP-rich phase and an LPA-rich phase. It is believed that the microvoid formation in the LPA-rich phase or at the interface is the main source of shrinkage compensation. The LPA-rich phase must reach a sufficiently high modulus in order to form microvoids, since a liquid LPA phase can release stress resulting from polymerization shrinkage. After gelation of the LPA-rich phase, the stress-induced local cracking caused by polymerization shrinkage in both phases is the main driving force for microvoid formation. It has been confirmed that a higher reaction rate in the LPA-rich phase provides more micro-cracking in the system to compensate for the volume shrinkage [[Li et al., 2000](#)]. The phase separation is accompanied by the partition of monomer, curing agents, and the nanoclay. It is speculated that most nanoclay will enter the LPA phase during the reaction-induced phase separation. This hypothesis is based on the fact that the LPA-rich phase consists of a large amount of styrene that shows good compatibility with clay, as well as the high polarity of PVAc that can help attract more clay to the LPA-rich phase.

We employed two methods to verify our hypothesis and visualize the clay partition during phase separation. One method was a temperature-forced phase separation to qualitatively assess the clay partition phase separation. The other method was the use of TEM to gather visual information about the clay spatial distribution in the cured sample. In the temperature-forced phase separation, a UP/St/LPA resin mixture with 3 wt% nanoclay was prepared. The resin mixture was mechanically stirred, followed by 2 hr sonication to achieve good clay dispersion. Then the sample was placed in a freezer at a temperature around -10°C . After several days the mixture was separated into two phases. The LPA-rich phase is the upper layer, while the UP-rich phase is the low layer. It appears that almost all of the clay went into the LPA-rich phase, even though the density of the nanoclay is higher than that of the UP resin. [Figure 4](#) shows the TEM micrograph of the UP/St/LPA sample with 1.5% 20A cured at room temperature. The bright images of the TEM micrograph reveal the formation of microvoids formed in the LPA-rich phase or at the interface, although some of the bright images came from the resin strip-off during sample preparation. The dark areas are the cured polymer matrix. Some small dark areas dispersed in the white area are believed to be the LPA-rich phase, while the large dark phase represents the UP-rich phase. The morphological observation clearly demonstrates that almost all of the clay platelets are distributed in the LPA-rich phase.

As revealed from TEM and temperature-forced phase separation, a very high concentration of nanoclay exists in the LPA-rich phase, which may facilitate phase separation. It can also result in a higher reaction rate there and substantially increases the polymer stiffness (modulus). The critical modulus for micro-cracking can be reached at a lower resin conversion in

the LPA-rich phase, compared to the system without nanoclay. Consequently, the volume expansion appears earlier and a better shrinkage control can be achieved.

Characterization of UP nanocomposites

X-ray and TEM were applied to analyze the morphology and structure of crosslinked polyester-clay nanocomposites. The X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns for the organically modified clay, Cloisite[®] 20A, and the unsaturated polyester-clay nanocomposites with different clay loading are shown in [Figure 5](#). The XRD curve for the organically modified MMT, Cloisite[®] 20A, shows a strong X-ray diffraction peak, with a characteristic gallery spacing of about 2.4 nm. For nanocomposites with a clay content of 3wt%, 5wt%, and 7wt%, the MMT gallery spacing increases from 2.4 nm to 3.5 nm, independent of the clay loading. The broadened peaks with less intensity are a characteristic of a highly disordered intercalated structure, i.e., a decrease in the degree of coherent layer stacking [[Vaia et al., 1996](#)].

Tensile properties

As shown in [Figure 6](#), the tensile moduli of UP/clay nanocomposites are superior to those of unmodified UP, as shown by a 16% improvement at 5% Cloisite 20A. After 5% loading, there is a slight decrease in the modulus. This maybe is the result of agglomeration of the clay particles. The modulus increase is higher than with the same content of a conventional micro-sized filler, such as calcium carbonate (5 wt% CaCO₃).

However, the enhancement in modulus comes with reductions in tensile strength and tensile strain, shown in [Figures 7a and 7b](#). This response is characteristic of materials reinforced with stiff materials and is particularly noticeable for the intercalated glassy nanocomposites [[Zerda et al., 2001](#)].

Fracture toughness

The fracture toughness parameter K_{IC} is presented as a function of nanoclay content in [Figure 8](#). The results demonstrate favorable toughness improvements of this brittle UP resin with the addition of a very small amount of nanoclay. At 5 wt% 20A, K_{IC} is 30% higher than that of the pure UP. The system with mixed nanoclay and CaCO₃ was found to be the most desirable one, which has the highest K_{IC} without sacrificing the tensile strength and tensile modulus. Detailed studies of the toughening mechanism in nanocomposites have not yet been undertaken.

CONCLUSION

In this study, results from density measurements showed that at a nanoclay content of 1-3 wt%, the UP/St/LPA system has much better volume shrinkage control. SEM was employed to observe the sample morphology. Nanoclay partition during phase separation was investigated by both temperature-induced phase separation and TEM observation of the cured sample. It showed that nearly all of the clay platelets resided in the LPA-rich phase, which tend to increase the reaction rate in the LPA-rich phase and early onset of critical modulus for micro-cracking. These two reasons could result in the earlier microvoid formation and volume expansion, leading to better shrinkage control of the UP/St/LPA systems cured at room temperature.

We investigated the mechanical properties and shrinkage control improvement of unsaturated polyester-clay nanocomposites cured at room temperature. X-ray and TEM were

used to analyze the clay dispersion. XRD results for UP nanocomposites with different clay contents showed weak and broad peaks, indicating that the silicate layers were intercalated by polymer molecules during mixing and the crosslinking reaction. The tensile moduli of UP/clay nanocomposites are superior to those of unmodified UP, with an improvement of 16% at 5% Cloisite 20A. However, the enhancements in moduli come with reductions in tensile strength. This response is characteristic of materials reinforced with stiff materials and is particularly noticeable for the intercalated glassy nanocomposites. The fracture toughness parameter K_{IC} showed favorable improvements with the addition of a very small amount of 20A. At 5wt% 20A, K_{IC} is 30% higher than that of the pure UP. The system with mixed nanoclay and CaCO_3 was found to be the most desirable one, which has the highest K_{IC} without sacrificing the tensile strength and tensile modulus.

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Table 1. Density and volume shrinkage of the samples cured at 26°C (3.5% LPA, 0.5% cobalt octoate, 1.5% MEKP, 300 ppm BQ).

	UP/St/LPA resin mixture ρ_{s_0} (g/cm ³)	Cured composite ρ_s (g/cm ³)	Volume shrinkage (%)
0% 20A	1.053	1.1319	6.96
1.5% 20A	1.0555	1.0879	2.97
3% 20A	1.0613	1.0462	-1.44
3% 20A, 0.25% Cobalt, 1.15% MEKP	1.0613	1.0841	2.11

Fig. 1. Reaction kinetics of UP/St/LPA system with different contents of 20A cured in 26°C water bath (0.5% cobalt octoate, 1.5% MEKP, 300ppm BQ, and 3.5% LPA): (a) reaction rate; (b) conversion.

Fig. 2. Reaction rate of UP/St/LPA system with different contents of 20A and initiator/promoter contents cured in 26°C water bath (300ppm BQ, and 3.5% LPA).

Fig. 3. SEM micrographs of cured UP/St/LPA system with different amounts of nanoclay cured in 26°C water bath (0.5% cobalt octoate, 1.5% MEKP, 300ppm BQ, and 3.5% LPA).

Fig. 4. TEM micrographs of UP/St/LPA system with 1.5% 20A cured at room temperature

Fig. 5. XRD patterns of UP nanocomposite with different 20A loading. Diffraction pattern of 20A is included as reference.

Fig. 6. Tensile modulus of UP nanocomposite as a function of 20A content.

Fig. 7. Tensile strength and tensile strain of UP nanocomposite as a function of 20A content.

Fig. 8. Fracture toughness parameters K_{1C} of UP nanocomposite presented as a function of nanoclay content.